

On the Essential Semantic Function of the Preterite Indicative (PPS) in Portuguese¹

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This is an English translation of a peer-reviewed article originally published in Japanese as: Makino, Shinya. (2010). *Porutogarugo no chokusetsuhō-kanzenkako no honshitsutekina imikinō ni tsuite* [On the essential semantic function of the Portuguese preterite indicative]. *Romansugo Kenkyū* [Studia Romanica], 43, 49–58. Tokyo: Nihon Romansugo Gakkai [Societas Japonica Studiorum Romanicorum]. To understand the semantic reanalysis of the PPC proposed in Makino (2025) — *A Perspective-and-Aspect-Driven System of Temporal Anchoring in Portuguese: Semantic Reanalysis of the Present Perfect and Other Cross-Romance Divergences* (Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15469071>) — understanding the functional competition between the PPC and the PPS is essential. This, in turn, requires a clear grasp of what the PPS fundamentally signifies. It is our belief that the present English translation contributes to this latter understanding. Note that **the present version includes moderate revisions and updates by the author**. These modifications have not undergone peer review.

Rusumo:

Em português, o Pretérito Perfeito Simples do Indicativo (ex. verbo *falar*: *falei, falaste, falou, falámos, falastes, falaram*) emprega-se para descrever um evento ou um estado já terminado no passado tanto sem relevância para o presente (ex. *Ele saiu mas voltou logo*) como com tal relevância (ex. *Ele não está. Já saiu para dar uma volta*). Este tempo verbal pode ter, para além disso, quase o mesmo valor temporal e aspectual que o Futuro Composto do Indicativo, substituindo-o frequentemente na oralidade com a co-ocorrência obrigatória do advérbio *já* (ex. *Amanhã por esta hora, já ele partiu / terá partido*). Se se considerasse um tempo puramente do passado, nem todos os seus usos acima mencionados poderiam explicar-se com facilidade, mas sim com base na seguinte interpretação: a função semântica essencial do Pretérito Perfeito

¹ This paper is based on an oral presentation given at the 49th Annual Conference of the Societas Japonica Studiorum Romanicorum, held at Hokkaido University on 31 May 2009.

Simples do Indicativo consiste em marcar o fim de uma situação, confirmado desde um ponto de perspectiva temporal situado num intervalo de tempo não delimitado que inclui necessariamente o momento da enunciação; não se explicita, porém, a continuação ou não do estado consequente da situação concluída até ao momento do dito ponto de perspectiva temporal.

Abstract:

In Portuguese, the *Pretérito Perfeito Simples do Indicativo* (e.g. verb *falar*: *falei, falaste, falou, falámos, falastes, falaram*) is used to describe an event or state that has already been completed in the past, both with no relevance to the present (e.g. *Ele saiu mas voltou logo* "He left but came back soon") and with such relevance (e.g. *Ele não está. Já saiu para dar uma volta* "He is not here. He has already gone for a walk"). This tense can also, in addition, have almost the same temporal and aspectual value as the *Futuro Composto do Indicativo*, often replacing it in spoken language with the obligatory co-occurrence of the adverb *já* (e.g. *Amanhã por esta hora, já ele partiu / terá partido* "By this time tomorrow, he will already have left"). If it were considered a purely past tense, not all of the aforementioned uses could be easily explained, but rather based on the following interpretation: the essential semantic function of the *Pretérito Perfeito Simples do Indicativo* is to encode the termination of a situation, confirmed from a temporal perspective point situated within an undelimited time interval that necessarily includes the speech time; however, the continuation or non-continuation of the result state of the terminated situation up to that point in time is not made explicit.

1. Introduction: the usage of the preterite indicative with the values of "past", "present perfect" and "future perfect"

In Contemporary Standard European Portuguese (henceforth simply *Portuguese*), the preterite indicative (*Pretérito Perfeito Simples do Indicativo*, henceforth *PPS*), unlike its etymologically cognate counterpart in other major Romance languages — the simple past in Contemporary French (*passé simple*), for example — is used across all registers not only to denote situations that terminated in the past without any relevance to the present situation, as in (1), but also, as in (2), to express a present-perfect value, and furthermore, as in (3), to indicate repeated situations that have terminated prior to present habitual situations:

(1) *Ele saiu mas voltou logo.* "He went out but came back soon after."²

(2) *Ele não está. Já saiu para dar uma volta.* "He's not here. He's already gone out for a walk."³

(3) *Quando eu chego ele já saiu, quando ele chega eu já sai.* "When I get home, he's already gone out; when he gets home, I've already gone out."

Moreover, in colloquial registers of everyday spoken language, as illustrated in (4), it is common for the PPS to be employed — with the same temporal and aspectual value — in place of the future perfect indicative, which is otherwise typically used primarily in more formal written registers:

(4) *Amanhã por esta hora, já ele saiu.* "He will already have gone out by this time tomorrow."

cf. *Amanhã por esta hora, ele já terá saído.* (future perfect indicative)

² The example sentences in this study are constructed from actual utterances observed by the author in spoken conversation and on the web. All examples were reviewed by two native speakers: a researcher at the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Coimbra at the time of the study (originally from Mealhada, near Coimbra, and a graduate of the Faculty of Sciences and Technology of the University of Coimbra), and a cultural officer at Coimbra City Hall and an anthropologist at the time of the study (born in Coimbra and a graduate of the Faculty of Letters of the University of Coimbra). With the exception of the colloquial examples in (4) and (25), all sentences were judged by them to be fully acceptable in both spoken and written registers of Standard European Portuguese.

³ In contrast to the simple preterite indicative, the use of the compound preterite indicative (*Pretérito Perfeito Composto do Indicativo* — *PPC*), formed with the present indicative of the auxiliary *ter* followed by the past participle in the masculine singular form, is highly restricted. Its primary function is to express situations that have continued from some point in the past up to the speech time, or that have been repeated during that interval. For instance, the sentence *Ele tem saído para dar uma volta* does not mean "He has gone out for a walk", but rather "He has been going out for walks lately", and is interpreted as denoting a repeated event extending from some point in the past up to the speech time.

In comparison with English, the PPS in Portuguese not only broadly covers the domains of *did* and *have done*, but also, in colloquial usage, appears to encroach upon the domain of *will have done*. In what follows, we shall examine example sentences involving the PPS from a temporal and aspectual perspective and, by considering its relationship with the present indicative, aim to elucidate the essential semantic function that underlies its various uses.

2. Basic usage: the speaker's temporal viewpoint at the speech time

"O Pretérito Perfeito... É, ..., sempre terminativo, isto é, marca um momento em que um estado ou um evento terminou" (Mateus et al. 2003: 156). Accordingly, it is difficult to use the PPS for situations whose termination cannot be confirmed. For instance, *A Terra girou à volta do Sol*, when presented without contextual or situational cues, is semantically and pragmatically infelicitous. This is because the termination of the situation *a Terra girar à volta do Sol* "the Earth revolving around the Sun" has not yet been confirmed at the present moment. Now, for a situation to be confirmed by the speaker as having terminated, and for this termination to be linguistically encoded, the *speaker's temporal viewpoint* — hereafter referred to simply as the *VP* — must be located after the termination point of the situation along the temporal axis. If the VP is located within the situation time — that is, the point or interval during which the situation holds — or prior to the initiation point of the situation, then the termination of the situation cannot be confirmed, although it may in some cases be anticipated or predicted. See the diagram (5) below, in which the thin horizontal line represents the temporal axis whereas the thick line represents the situation time, and the black dot (●) at the end of the thick line indicates the termination point:

In what follows, we shall examine where the VP is located when describing a situation by means of the PPS and how the PPS relates to the state resulting from the termination of the situation, taking into account the *Aktionsart* of the predicate and related encyclopedic knowledge. The classification of *Aktionsart* in this study follows Vendler (1968) and Moens & Steedman (1988).

Examples (6) and (7) below involve predicates whose *Aktionsart* is that of a *culmination* or *achievement*. A culmination is a type of *telic situation*, and refers specifically to the termination

point itself of a process that has an inherent terminal point — namely, the necessary endpoint:

(6) *Ele morreu*. "He died."

(7) *Ele saiu do Brasil*. "He left / went out from Brazil."

In (6) and (7), the use of the PPS indicates that the situation's reaching of its inherent terminal point is confirmed from the VP, which is located at the speech time⁴. The next issue concerns how the *result state* arising from the termination of the situation is treated. In (6), the result state *ele estar morto*, following from the termination of the situation *ele morrer*, is typically *inferred* to continue up to the speech time — as illustrated in (8), where the dashed line represents the result state — unless special circumstances or contexts such as "he came back to life" are introduced. This inference results from the fact that the situation referred to by the predicate *morrer* usually occurs only once per animate entity and is normally not repeatable:

In (6), in contrast, whether the result state *ele estar fora do Brasil*, following from the termination of the situation *ele sair do Brasil*, continues to hold up to the speech time where the VP is located remains unclear unless supported by contextual or/and situational cues, as shown in (9). This is because, unlike *morrer* in (5), the *situation-base* denoted by the predicate *sair do Brasil* is in principle repeatable⁵:

Examples (10) and (11) below involve predicates whose *Aktionsart* is that of a *state*. A state is a type of *atelic situation* — that is, a non-bounded situation lacking an inherent terminal point —

⁴ What is stated here with respect to *culmination* also applies to what is known as a *culminated process* or *accomplishment*. This too is a type of *telic situation*, but unlike a culmination, it represents both a process with an inherent terminal point and the terminal point itself — e.g. *comer o bolo* "to eat the cake"; *ir ao museu* "to go to the museum".

⁵ The *situation-base* here refers to the fundamental schematic structure of a situation — a structure that becomes an actual situation when participants are integrated into it. Conversely, a situation-base can be understood as what remains of a situation when its participants are abstracted away.

which, moreover, does not exhibit dynamic progression or *dynamicity*. In being non-bounded, lacking dynamicity and possessing inherent continuity, this *Aktionsart* stands in opposition, in all of its feature specifications, to *culmination*, as exemplified in (6) and (7):

(10) *Ele foi professor*. "He was a teacher."

(11) *Ele esteve em casa*. "He was at home."

In (10) and (11), the PPS introduces extrinsically a terminal point into what is originally a non-bounded situation — that is, an aspectual shift takes place — and encodes the fact that this termination is confirmed from the speech-time VP⁶. In (10), the negative state *ele não ser professor*, which follows from the termination of the situation *ele ser professor*, is generally inferred to continue up to the speech time — as indicated in (12) — unless there is contextual or/and situational information suggesting, for example, that he returned to the teaching profession after resigning. This is because the repetition of the situation-base denoted by the predicate *ser professor* is, from the perspective of encyclopaedic knowledge, generally not easy:

In (11), by contrast, whether the negative state *ele não estar em casa*, which follows from the termination of the situation *ele estar em casa*, continues to hold up to the speech time remains indeterminate unless supported by contextual or/and situational cues, as shown in (13). This is because the situation-base denoted by the predicate *estar em casa* is, in general, repeatable:

From the analysis of examples (6) (7) (10) (11), the following observations (14)-(17) concerning the nature of the PPS may be drawn:

(14) The PPS presents a telic situation as having culminated in its intrinsic terminal point, and

⁶ What is stated here with respect to *state* also applies to what is known as a *process* or *activity*. This too is a type of atelic situation, but unlike a state, it exhibits dynamic development and allows for internal pauses — e.g. *comer bolos* "to eat cakes"; *nadar* "to swim".

an atelic situation as having concluded by the imposition of an extrinsic terminal point.

(15) The terminal point of the situation in (14) is confirmed from the VP located at the speech time.

(16) The result state or negative state following from the termination of the situation in (14) may, in some cases, be inferred by the hearer to continue up to the speech time. Such an inference appears, however, not to rely on the telic/atelic classification of predicates — that is, on their aspectual classes — but on encyclopaedic knowledge concerning the repeatability of the situation-base referred to by the predicate, as well as on contextual or/and situational cues.

(17) it follows from (16) that the PPS itself does not possess the function of explicitly encoding the continuation of the result state or negative state up to the speech time — a function typically associated with the English present perfect, for example, and characteristic of the perfect aspect.

By contrast, the addition of the temporal adverb *já* to the examples (6) and (7) yields the following interpretations:

(18) *Ele já saiu do Brasil.* "He has already left Brazil." / "He has been out of Brazil before."

(19) *Ele já foi professor.* "He was once a teacher." / "He has been a teacher before."

In (18), the result state *ele estar fora do Brasil*, which follows from the termination of the situation *ele sair do Brasil*, continues up to the speech time, which is made explicit by the adverb *já*, as indicated in (20). On the other hand, (18) may be used even if the referent of *ele* is currently in Brazil. In such cases, the sentence expresses the subject referent's experience. In other words, what *já* makes explicit is the ownership of past experience resulting from the terminated situation — *ele ter a experiência de ter saído do Brasil* — also as shown in (20):

Similarly, in (19), the adverb *já* makes it explicit that either the negative state *ele não ser professor*, following from the termination of the situation *ele ser professor* or the ownership of past experience *ele ter a experiência de ter sido professor* continues up to the speech time, as in (21):

Interestingly, unlike the construction "*already* + present perfect" in English, Portuguese allows the co-occurrence of "*já* + PPS" with an adverbial that explicitly refers to a past time, as in (22):

(22) *Já acabei o trabalho ontem.* "I've already finished the work + I finished it yesterday."

cf. **I have already finished the work yesterday.*

In (22), the confirmation of the situation's termination is encoded by the PPS, the specific point of termination is referred to by the temporal adverbial *ontem* and the continuation of the result state following from the situation's termination up to the speech time is made explicit by *já*.

Based on the analysis of (18) (19) (22), the following remark can be added to the considerations (14)–(17), as (23):

(23) What the PPS encodes is merely the confirmation, from the VP located at the speech time, of the termination of a situation to be described — that is, its aspect is strictly *terminative*. Accordingly, for the continuation up to the speech time of the result state, the negative state or the ownership of experience following from the termination of the situation to be made explicit, the adverb *já* needs to be used, as shown in (24)⁷:

⁷ The original version of this section concluded with the following remark: "Such present-perfect-like uses of the simple preterite are to be seen as filling a functional gap left by the compound form Pretérito Perfeito Composto do Indicativo, which is unable to express both the termination of a situation and its result state." However, subsequent research has shown that this interpretation was mistaken, and the passage has therefore been removed from the present translation.

3. Other usage: the speaker's temporal viewpoint *not* at the speech time

The PPS is not restricted to cases in which the VP is located at the speech time, as shown in (25):

(25) *Amanhã por esta hora, já ele saiu de casa.* "By this time tomorrow, he will already have left the house."

In (25), the termination of the situation *ele sair de casa* is anticipated or expected to be confirmed from the future time *amanhã por esta hora*, and this confirmation is encoded by the PPS. That is, the difference between (6) (7) (10) (11) (18) (19) (22) and (25) lies in the temporal location of the VP from which the termination of the situation is confirmed. In (6) (7) (10) (11) (18) (19) (22), the VP is located at the speech time, whereas in (25), it is located at a future time — explicitly specified by the adverbial *amanhã por esta hora* — which is posterior to the speech time. Furthermore, the use of *já* in (25) makes it explicit that the result state *ele estar fora de casa*, which follows from the termination of the situation *ele sair de casa*, is expected to continue up to the future time *amanhã por esta hora*, as in (26). When the PPS bears temporal and aspectual value equivalent to that of the future perfect indicative in this way, the use of *já* is obligatory:

In Portuguese, the essential oppositive value of the future perfect indicative with respect to the PPS is assumed to be its *modal* value — that is, the encoding of the speaker's belief in the possibility of the occurrence of a situation. In practice, especially in colloquial usage, it is not common for the future perfect to be used with purely *temporal* value⁸. Precisely because the future perfect tends to be less functional as a tense form in spoken Portuguese, it is the PPS that comes to occupy this temporal and aspectual domain — a fact that accounts for the frequent use of the PPS with future-perfect-like value.

The final example (27) illustrates a case in which the VP is located neither at a single speech-time

⁸ The future perfect indicative is more commonly used with a modal reading — that is, to express an assumption about the termination of a situation as inferred from the VP located at the speech time — as in *Ele terá perdido o comboio* "He will have missed the train", which contrasts with the factual assertion *Ele perdeu o comboio* "He missed the train" (cf. Mateus et al. 2003: 164).

point nor at a single future-time point:

(27) *Quando eu chego ele já saiu, quando ele chega eu já saí.* "When I get back, he has already gone out; when he gets back, I have already gone out."

In (27), the termination of the situation *ele sair* precedes the VP located at *quando eu chego*, and the termination of *eu sair* precedes the VP located at *quando ele chega*. Since the construction "quando + present indicative" denotes present habitual repetition, the VPs *quando eu chego* and *quando ele chega* do not correspond to single points on the temporal axis, but rather to multiple unspecified points within a time interval that includes the speech time and extends indeterminately both before and after it. Moreover, the result state *ele estar fora* following from the termination of *ele sair*, and *eu estar fora* from *eu sair*, are both understood to continue up to the respective VPs *quando eu chego* and *quando ele chega* — and this continuity is explicitly indicated by the use of the adverb *já*, as in (28), where "term." stands for "termination":

Based on the analysis of the examples (25) and (27) above, the consideration (15) must be reformulated as (29):

(29) The terminal point of the situation in (14) is one that is confirmed from the VP, which may be located at the speech time, at a future time or at multiple unspecified points within a time interval that includes the speech time and extends indeterminately both before and after it. Unless the VP is located at the speech time, its temporal location is specified by the context. That is, the default location of the VP is at the speech time.

4. Conclusion: the essential function of the preterite indicative and its oppositive relation to the present indicative

What becomes clear from the considerations (14) (29) (16) (17), obtained through the analysis in

Sections 2 and 3, is that the essential function of the PPS is to encode the confirmation, from the VP located on the temporal axis, of the termination of the situation referred to by the clause or sentence. The issue, then, is where the VP is located. It may be at the speech time, at a future time or at multiple unspecified points within a time interval that includes the speech time and extends before and after it. All these possibilities are alike, however, in that the VP is located at some point within a time interval that includes the speech time and opens bidirectionally along the temporal axis. If we refer to this interval as the *non-past* and distinguish it from the *past* — the other time interval that excludes the speech time — we arrive at the conclusion stated in (30):

(30) The essential semantic function of the PPS is to encode the termination of a situation to be described as confirmed from the VP located within the *non-past* time interval. The default location of the VP is at the speech time and, unless it is located at the speech time, its temporal location is specified by the context. Furthermore, the PPS itself does not possess the function of explicitly indicating that the result state, the negative state or the ownership of past experience following from the termination of the situation continues up to the time at which the VP is located: such continuation is either inferred from contextual or/and situational cues or made explicit by the temporal adverb *já*.

Since the PPS is one of the terms constituting the mood-tense-aspect system of Portuguese, its semantic function cannot be fully defined without considering its oppositional relations with the other terms within the same system. In what follows, we shall examine its opposition to the present indicative — *Presente do Indicativo*, henceforth *PI* — which constitutes a minimal semantic pair with the PPS, in order to explore what is entailed by the confirmation of a situation's termination from the VP located within the *non-past* time interval.

The PI and the PPS, in opposition to the present and present perfect subjunctives, do not suspend the judgment/commitment concerning the truth value of a sentence. In opposition to the future and future perfect indicatives, they do not encode the speaker's belief in the possibility of the occurrence of a situation. They are also identical in that they both locate the VP for describing situations at any point within the *non-past* time interval — though the default location is at the speech time. The PI is opposed, however, to the PPS in that it is employed when the termination of the situation is not confirmed from the VP and, in this respect, the PI and the PPS constitute a minimal semantic opposition. See the following examples (31)-(34):

(31) *Ele está em casa.* "He is at home."

(32) *Ele fuma.* "He smokes."

(33) *A Terra gira à volta do Sol.* "The Earth revolves around the Sun."

(34) *Ele amanhã vem cá.* "He is coming here tomorrow."

In (31)-(33), the situations described are, respectively: a state that holds at the speech time, an event that habitually repeats within an indefinite time interval including the speech time and an event that holds at any point within an indefinite time interval that includes the speech time. It is therefore impossible to confirm the termination of these situations from the VP located at the speech time. In (34), which refers to a certain near-future event, the event is only anticipated to certainly occur at the future time *amanhã* and, once again, the termination of the situation cannot be confirmed from the VP located at the speech time. Thus, the relationship between the PI and the PPS can be schematically represented as in (35):

The distinction between whether the termination of a situation is confirmed or not appears to be crucial for human beings. This is because a situation of which the termination is confirmed can be rephrased as an entity upon which human intervention is no longer possible, whereas a situation of which the termination is not confirmed is one upon which it remains possible. Similarly, the distinction between the *non-past* and *past* time intervals, within which the VP for describing situations is located, is also significant. This is because the *past* represents a world in which one can no longer live and where human intervention is no longer possible, while the *non-past* represents a world in which one is alive and where it is still possible to live and intervene. In other words, **the opposition between the PI and the PPS can be said to linguistically encode a basic cognitive distinction, viewed from a world in which human intervention is possible, between situations upon which human intervention is possible and ones upon which it is no longer possible.**

Reference:

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